

A Convolution Neural Network with Optimal Filter Set for Medical Image Processing

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Abstract— The present paper proposes the extraction of Optimal Number of Filter Set and thereby Optimal Filter Set in Convolution Neural Network during its application in Medical Image Processing. This work involves medical applications namely Classifying ECG on the basis of types of Arrhythmias. We have used Convolution Neural Network, where we have optimized the Filter Number and Filter Set for learning ECG Data Set. We have extracted the Optimal Filter Set for the above medical data set, during the training of the Convolution Neural Network. The present paper thus focuses into the optimal set of filters in a Convolution Neural Network model which is bound to exhibit the maximum overall accuracy of classification. The work achieves an accuracy of classification of different types of Arrhythmias of 97.56% with 59 optimal number of filters. Over and above, as and when the optimized learned Optimal Filter Set is applied during recognition or detection of Arrhythmia the time taken for recognition is also thereby minimized.

Keywords— Artificial Neural Network, Convolution Neural Network, Medical Image Processing, Optimal Filter Set, Arrhythmia Classification

I. INTRODUCTION

Medical Image Processing for detection of different diseases has achieved a tremendous impact in present day. Diseases like heart abnormality may be detected from electrocardiogram (ECG) signals. In our present work we have used Convolution Neural Network (CNN) as a basic tool to detect this diseases. The CNNs to detect the above diseases are optimized in such a way that during learning the CNNs learn (with the corresponding ECG data set) to detect the arrhythmia type extracting optimal set and optimal number of filters. After the learning is over, those different CNNs are fielded to detect the different arrhythmia types. As the CNNs learn the disease detection with optimal filter set, the moderate accuracy is reliable – and at the same time the time for recognition of diseases is a minimum.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Zhaohan Xiong et al.[1] have developed RhythmNet, a 21-layer 1D convolutional recurrent neural network, to classify ECGs of different rhythms including AF automatically. We

evaluated our algorithm on 3,658 testing data and obtained an F1 accuracy of 82% for classifying sinus rhythm, AF, and other arrhythmias. RhythmNet was also ranked 5th in the 2017 CinC challenge.

A. Chowdhury [2] In their deep learning algorithms are quite good at distinguishing between normal and abnormal cardiac rhythms by gathering complex morphological components from ECG data. Additionally, by combining CNNs with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, performance is enhanced, leading to a hybrid CNN-LSTM framework that can more precisely and successfully classify cardiac abnormalities.

P. Rajkapur [3] developed and validated a deep learning algorithm that classified clinically important abnormalities in chest radiographs at a performance level comparable to practicing radiologists. Once tested prospectively in clinical settings, the algorithm could have the potential to expand patient access to chest radiograph diagnostics.

S. Trivubanam et al., [4], included pre-processing and segmentation of ECG. Extraction of ECG features are to support the ECG beat classification and analysis of cardiac. The proposed arrhythmia classifier results in an accuracy up to 98% for various classes of arrhythmia considered in this work. Novelty/Applications

III. THEORY OF OPERATION

The most current technique for the extraction of various patterns from a set of images to specifically recognize the class of those images for the specific task of image recognition, the latest state of the art methodology is to implement a Convolution Neural Network (CNN) [5,8]. In this type of Artificial Neural Network (ANN), the image specific features or attributes are conveniently drawn out and encoded in the network with the help of programmed or previously learned filters of kernels. These features which are conventionally termed as ‘kernels’, are specific for a particular type of image data set. With this, the CNN [4-6] is one much improved technique for complex pattern recognition tasks and provides more reliable and better

performance evaluation in terms of accuracy etc. as well as effectiveness and efficiency.

CNN [5,8] can be used to classify medical images which can have various applications in the fields of diagnosis. It is faster, more accurate and by adjusting the hyper parameters, the accuracy can be increased greatly.

We are dealing here the Medical Images for Arrhythmia Classification by differentiating arrhythmia types (N: Normal or Non-ectopic Beats:

S: Ectopic beats Supra Ventricular V: Ectopic beats Ventricular
F: Fusion Beats Q :Unknown Beats

based on Electro Cardiogram (ECG) scans)

Here benchmark datasets have been used to create CNN models, with varying hyper parameters to achieve maximum accuracy.

A. Classification and Detection of types of Arrhythmias

The heart's rhythm and electrical activity can be tested with the help of electrocardiogram (ECG). This detects the electrical signals produced by one's heart during its beatings. These signal plots are recorded and read out by a medical practitioner to find out any abnormality. Instead of a medical practitioner, we can use a CNN which will learn the different arrhythmias from a pre-processed recorded training dataset and when the learning is over, will be able to detect the types of arrhythmias [3]

B. The different types of arrhythmias

- 1) Normal Ectopic beats: These suggest a normal heart beat.
- 2) Supraventricular Ectopic Beats: These beats are atrial contractions triggered by ectopic foci rather than the sinoatrial node.
- 3) Ventricular Ectopic Beats: In daily clinical practice these are most commonly found out. While these are largely asymptomatic, can also cause upsetting symptoms in some patients.
- 4) Fusion Beats: These occur when a supraventricular and a ventricular impulse coincide thereby producing a hybrid complex.
- 5) Unknown Beats: These do not follow under any specific category and can be a mixture of the above types of arrhythmia.

IV. METHODOLOGY AND SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

We have designed and developed CNN architecture to analyse the different types of arrhythmias for diagnosis by a medical practitioner. During learning phase this learns the different arrhythmia and after the learning is over recognizes the arrhythmia.

Fig 1 CNN to detect different types of Arrhythmias

V. RESULTS

System Details are as below:

Hardware
RAM: 6 GB
PROCESSOR: INTEL I7
Software
OS: WINDOWS 10
Anaconda
Platform: Python 3 + Keras

We use Holdout Method where a portion of data set is set aside for performance evaluation.

In the graph of accuracy vs. no. of filters we find the location of stable accuracy. The percentage similarity among the filter set is calculated as below:

Tolerance for intensity of each weight of the kernel = 20 [intensity scale = 0-255]

Tolerance to decide two filters identical [i.e. if two filters have at most 7 weights same (with the tolerance of above point 6) then they should be considered identical)

An Anaconda environment (Spyder IDE) was used to execute the program.

A. Classification and Detection of types of Arrhythmias

Benchmark dataset used:

<https://www.kaggle.com/shayanfazeli/heartbeat>

Fig 2 Few examples of different types of Arrhythmias

Fig 5 Heatmap Confusion Matrix

Fig. 3 Accuracy vs. No. of filters of the CNN for types of Arrhythmia detection

Serial no.	Number of Filters	Accuracy during training of optimal number of filters	Time taken for training(sec)	Accuracy during prediction of optimal number of filters	Time taken for prediction(sec)
1.	59	97.56%	476	97.56%	393
2.	60	97.56%	494	97.32%	410
3.	61	97.56%	518	96.89%	428

Table 2 No. of filters and the corresponding performance evaluations

No. of Filters	Accuracy
59	97.56%
60	97.32%
61	96.89%

Table 1 No. of Filters vs. Accuracy

Fig 4 Venn Diagram

VI. CONCLUSION

This proposed work involves medical applications namely Classifying ECG on the basis of types of Arrhythmias. We have used Convolution Neural Network. Here we have optimized the Filter Number and Filter Set for learning ECG Data Set. We have extracted the Optimal Filter Set for the above during the training of the Convolution Neural Network. The present paper thus focuses into the optimal set of filters in a Convolution Neural Network model which is bound to exhibit the maximum overall accuracy of classification. The work achieves an accuracy of classification of different types of Arrhythmias of 97.56% during prediction with 59 optimal number of filters. Also, as and when the optimized learned Optimal Filter Set is applied during recognition or detection of Arrhythmia the time taken for recognition is also thereby minimized.

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